

Sigmoid Volvulus Presenting as Large Bowel Obstruction in an Elderly Patient with Diabetes and Hypertension: A Case Report Emphasizing Timely Surgical Management

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ABSTRACT

Sigmoid volvulus, a potentially life-threatening large bowel obstruction, is caused by torsion of the sigmoid colon around its mesenteric axis. It commonly occurs in elderly patients with predisposing factors such as chronic constipation, long sigmoid loop, and comorbidities that increase operative risk. Rapid diagnosis and timely surgical management are essential to prevent ischemic necrosis and perforation. A 67-year-old man with a history of hypertension and diabetes mellitus presented with intermittent colicky abdominal pain and distension for three days, accompanied by constipation and failure to pass flatus. There was no vomiting or fever. Clinical examination revealed a distended abdomen with diffuse tenderness but no guarding or rigidity. Investigations demonstrated leukocytosis, normal liver and renal profiles, and radiographic features of large bowel obstruction suggestive of sigmoid volvulus. The patient was optimized for surgery, and emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperatively, a twisted and dilated sigmoid colon with ascitic fluid was found. The procedure included detorsion, resection of the redundant sigmoid segment, primary anastomosis, proximal transverse colostomy, and peritoneal toilet. Postoperatively, the patient recovered uneventfully apart from mild respiratory distress. Progressive dietary advancement and colostomy function were satisfactory. After six weeks, colonoscopy and distal loop colonogram confirmed a healthy anastomosis, and colostomy closure was successfully performed. Follow-up at three months showed complete recovery and return to normal activities. This case emphasizes that early recognition and prompt surgical intervention in sigmoid volvulus, even in elderly and comorbid patients, can achieve excellent outcomes. A staged approach with proximal diversion during initial surgery minimizes anastomotic complications and ensures safe restoration of bowel continuity after recovery.

KEYWORDS: Sigmoid volvulus, large bowel obstruction, elderly, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, resection and anastomosis, transverse colostomy, laparotomy.

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INTRODUCTION

Sigmoid volvulus is a surgical emergency characterized by torsion of the sigmoid colon on its mesenteric axis, leading to luminal obstruction and vascular compromise (1). It accounts for approximately 5–10% of all intestinal obstructions globally and up to 50% of cases in regions

where redundant sigmoid colon and high-fiber diets are prevalent (3). The condition is more common in elderly men, often with a background of chronic constipation or neurological illness (5).

The clinical presentation varies depending on the duration and severity of the volvulus (1). Early stages may present intermittent colicky abdominal pain, distension, and

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constipation, whereas prolonged torsion may lead to bowel ischemia, necrosis, and perforation (4). Prompt diagnosis and intervention are vital, as delays significantly increase morbidity and mortality rates (7).

The pathogenesis of sigmoid volvulus involves anatomical predisposition, including a long and mobile sigmoid colon with a narrow mesenteric base (2). Risk factors include chronic constipation, institutionalization, neurological disorders, and advanced age (6). In developing countries, dietary habits rich in indigestible fiber and sedentary lifestyles contribute to higher incidence (10).

Radiological diagnosis is critical in suspected cases. A plain abdominal radiograph often shows the characteristic “coffee-bean” or “omega loop” sign. Ultrasonography and CT imaging further confirm the diagnosis and assess bowel viability. Endoscopic decompression can be both diagnostic and therapeutic in selected patients without ischemia (4,5).

Surgical management remains the cornerstone of treatment, especially in complicated or recurrent cases. Options range from simple detorsion and sigmoidopexy to resection and primary anastomosis with or without a diverting stoma (5). In high-risk or unstable patients, staged operations such as Hartmann’s procedure or resection with proximal colostomy are preferred to reduce mortality (7).

Here, we report a case of sigmoid volvulus in a 67-year-old diabetic and hypertensive patient managed successfully with emergency resection, anastomosis, and proximal diversion, followed by elective colostomy closure. This case highlights the importance of timely diagnosis, multidisciplinary perioperative care, and careful surgical planning in elderly patients with comorbidities.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 67-year-old man presented to the surgical emergency department with complaints of intermittent, colicky abdominal pain for three days, associated with abdominal distension, constipation, and absence of flatus. The pain was generalized, moderate in intensity, and progressive in nature. He denied nausea, vomiting, hematemesis, melena, or fever. His bowel habits had been irregular for several months, but there was no history of similar episodes before. He was a known case of hypertension, previously with a maximum blood pressure of 170/90 mmHg, controlled with regular medication. He was also a diabetic under treatment with oral hypoglycemics for more than 10 years. There was no history of coronary artery disease, stroke, or renal impairment. He had no known drug allergy and no prior abdominal surgery.

On admission, he was conscious, oriented, and cooperative. His vital signs were temperature 36.5°C, blood pressure 120/70 mmHg, pulse 100 beats/min, respiratory rate 22/min, and oxygen saturation 96% on room air. There was no pallor, icterus, cyanosis, clubbing, or pedal edema.

Abdominal examination revealed distension, diffuse tenderness, and tympanic percussion notes, with no palpable mass or organomegaly. There was no guarding or rigidity. Bowel sounds were hyperactive. Per rectal examination revealed an empty rectum.

Laboratory investigations showed hemoglobin 13.6 g/dL, total WBC count $20.1 \times 10^9/L$, platelet count $185 \times 10^9/L$, ESR 30 mm/hr, blood urea 35 mg/dL, and serum creatinine 0.4 mg/dL. Liver function tests and coagulation profile (PT, INR) were within normal limits. Serum electrolytes were normal. HbA1C was 10.6%, indicating poor long-term glycemic control. Hepatitis C antibody was reactive, but HBsAg and HIV were non-reactive.

A chest X-ray revealed prominent bronchovascular markings, suggestive of mild chest infection (Figure 1). Plain abdominal X-ray demonstrated bean shaped dilated bowel in central and lower abdomen (Figure 2 & 3), highly suggestive of sigmoid volvulus. Abdominal ultrasonography showed fluid-filled loops of both small and large bowel with mild free fluid in the pelvis, confirming large bowel obstruction.

Figure 1. Chest X-ray showing prominent bilateral bronchovascular markings, suggestive of mild chest infection.

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Figure 2. Plain abdominal X-ray (erect) showing a bean-shaped dilated bowel loop in the central and lower abdomen, suggestive of sigmoid volvulus.

Figure 3. Plain abdominal X-ray (supine) showing a markedly dilated, bean-shaped sigmoid colon with a central curvilinear line, consistent with sigmoid volvulus.

Electrocardiography (ECG) showed sinus tachycardia (114 bpm). Echocardiography revealed normal left ventricular systolic function (LVEF 68%), grade I diastolic dysfunction, and no evidence of valvular disease, pericardial effusion, or

intracardiac thrombus. Cardiology and endocrinology consultations deemed the patient to be at intermediate risk for surgery.

After preoperative optimization, including correction of dehydration and electrolyte imbalance, emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed under general anesthesia. Intraoperative findings revealed a grossly distended sigmoid colon twisted around its mesenteric axis, consistent with sigmoid volvulus (Figure 4 & 5). The small and large bowel loops were dilated and fluid-filled, with mild ascitic fluid. The bowel was viable with no evidence of ischemia or perforation. The procedure included detorsion of the sigmoid loop, decompression, resection of the redundant sigmoid segment, end-to-end primary anastomosis, proximal transverse colostomy for diversion, peritoneal toilet, and drainage tube placement (Figure 6, 7, 8, 9 & 10). Hemostasis was secured, and the abdomen was closed in layers.

Figure 4. Intraoperative view of a markedly distended sigmoid colon with axial torsion, confirming sigmoid volvulus.

Figure 5. Intraoperative view of sigmoid volvulus with gross colonic distension and mesenteric twist.

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Figure 6. Operative view of the sigmoid colon after detorsion of volvulus, showing gross dilatation with viable bowel.

Figure 9. End-to-end primary anastomosis after resection of redundant sigmoid colon.

Figure 7. Intraoperative view of the sigmoid colon after decompression, showing reduced tension with viable bowel.

Figure 10. Intraoperative view of a proximal transverse loop colostomy for faecal diversion.

Figure 8. Resection of the redundant sigmoid colon after decompression and reduction of volvulus.

The patient was transferred to the surgical ward for close monitoring. Oxygen supplementation, intravenous fluids, broad-spectrum antibiotics, and insulin infusion were initiated. Mild postoperative respiratory distress was managed conservatively with bronchodilators and chest physiotherapy. Postoperative laboratory tests showed a reduction of WBC from $20.1 \times 10^9/L$ to $7 \times 10^9/L$ by the fifth postoperative day. Mild hypokalemia was noted and corrected with intravenous potassium supplementation. The colostomy became functional by the second postoperative day, and bowel decompression was satisfactory. Oral feeding was resumed gradually from clear liquids to a full diet. The surgical wound healed without infection. The patient was discharged on postoperative day 12 in good general condition, with advice for stoma care, respiratory exercises, and follow-up.

At two-week and one-month follow-ups, the patient reported a good appetite, adequate colostomy function, and normal bowel habits. After six weeks, colonoscopy revealed normal mucosa and a healthy anastomosis (Figure 11). Distal loop

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colonography confirmed patent continuity and absence of leakage (Figure 12 & 13). Elective colostomy closure was performed successfully (Figure 14).

Figure 11. Colonoscopic views showing normal colonic mucosa and intact anastomosis

Figure 12. Distal loop colonogram (AP view) showing a patent distal loop without leakage.

Figure 13. Distal loop colonogram (lateral view) showing a patent distal loop without leakage.

Figure 14. Intraoperative view of colostomy closure following confirmation of distal loop patency.

The postoperative period after the second surgery was uneventful. The patient tolerated a normal diet within five days and resumed normal bowel activity. At two-week, one-month, and three-month follow-ups, he was asymptomatic, active, and had returned to his daily routine.

DISCUSSION

Sigmoid volvulus accounts for a significant proportion of colonic obstructions, especially in elderly populations. The twisting of the sigmoid loop causes closed-loop obstruction, which may compromise blood flow, leading to ischemia, gangrene, and perforation if not managed promptly (7).

The incidence of sigmoid volvulus varies geographically. It is particularly common in Africa, the Middle East, and Asia, where high-fiber diets predispose to elongation of the sigmoid colon. In developed countries, it often affects institutionalized elderly patients with comorbidities and reduced mobility (8, 10).

Our patient presented with classical features of sigmoid volvulus—abdominal distension, colicky pain, constipation, and absence of flatus. The absence of vomiting or peritonitis signs suggested an early stage of obstruction without gangrene. These findings highlight the importance of clinical suspicion in elderly patients presenting with distension and constipation.

Radiographic evaluation remains essential in diagnosis. The plain abdominal X-ray “coffee-bean” sign, coupled with ultrasound findings, confirmed our suspicion. In some cases, CT imaging is used to demonstrate the “whirl sign” of twisted mesentery.

Initial management includes fluid resuscitation, correction of electrolytes, and decompression. Non-operative decompression using sigmoidoscopy may be attempted in stable, non-strangulated patients. However, recurrence rates after endoscopic detorsion are high, ranging from 40–70% (9, 10).

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Surgical treatment remains definitive. In our case, emergency resection and primary anastomosis with proximal diversion was chosen, considering the patient's comorbidities and risk of anastomotic leak. This approach allowed decompression while preventing recurrent volvulus and sepsis.

The decision to perform a proximal diverting colostomy in elderly, diabetic patients is supported by evidence showing reduced postoperative complications, especially anastomotic leak, in compromised bowel or borderline vascular conditions. This staged approach allows safe restoration after the patient's metabolic and nutritional recovery.

Respiratory complications are frequent in elderly postoperative patients, particularly those with underlying bronchovascular changes, as in this case. Aggressive pulmonary care and early mobilization prevented prolonged morbidity.

Follow-up colonoscopy and colonogram confirmed complete recovery, and elective colostomy closure restored bowel continuity. This case underlines the safety of staged surgery in elderly and medically compromised individuals.

Overall, successful management of sigmoid volvulus in elderly patients requires early recognition, comprehensive preoperative optimization, judicious surgical decision-making, and meticulous postoperative care. In resource-limited settings, careful clinical evaluation and timely intervention can achieve outcomes comparable to high-resource environments.

CONCLUSION

Sigmoid volvulus remains a critical cause of large bowel obstruction in elderly patients. Timely diagnosis, surgical intervention, and a tailored staged approach are key to minimizing morbidity and mortality. This case demonstrates that even in high-risk diabetic and hypertensive patients, good outcomes are achievable with appropriate perioperative care and multidisciplinary management.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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REFERENCES

- I. Atamanalp, S.S. 2013. Sigmoid volvulus: Diagnosis in 938 patients over 45.5 years. *Tech Coloproctol.* 2013, 17(4): 419-424.
- II. Perrot, L., Fohlen, A., Alves, A., and Lubrano, J. 2015. Management of the sigmoid volvulus: Short- and long-term results of primary resection. *Dis Colon Rectum.* 2015, 58(1): 79-84.
- III. Ballantyne, G.H. 1982. Review of sigmoid volvulus: History and results of treatment. *Dis Colon Rectum.* 1982, 25(5): 494-501.
- IV. Raveenthiran, V., Madiba, T.E., Atamanalp, S.S., and De, U. 2010. Volvulus of the sigmoid colon. *Colorectal Dis.* 2010, 12(7): e1-e17.
- V. Gingold, D., and Murrell, Z. 2012. Management of colonic volvulus. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg.* 2012, 25(4): 236-244.
- VI. Osiro, S., Cunningham, D., Shoja, M.M., Tubbs, R.S., Gielecki, J., and Loukas, M. 2012. The twisted colon: A review of sigmoid volvulus. *Am Surg.* 2012, 78(3): 271-279.
- VII. Halabi, W.J. et al. 2014. Colonic volvulus in the United States: Trends, outcomes, and predictors of mortality. *Ann Surg.* 2014, 259(2): 293-301.
- VIII. Shimizu, Y. et al. 2017. Surgical management and outcomes of sigmoid volvulus: Experience from a tertiary hospital. *World J Surg.* 2017, 41(9): 2483-2489.
- IX. Tan, K.K., Wong, J., and Sim, R. 2010. Non-operative treatment of sigmoid volvulus: Recurrence and risk factors. *Am J Surg.* 2010, 200(6): 715-719.
- X. Heis, H.A. et al. 2008. Sigmoid volvulus in the Middle East. *World J Surg.* 2008, 32(3): 459-464.